

**ISSUES STRENGTHENING THE FOOD BASE IN ANIMAL HUSBANDRY – A
FACTOR OF INCREASING PRODUCTIVITY**

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the legal basis for the development of the livestock industry in Uzbekistan, the opportunities and prospects of the Syrdarya region in this area. Scientifically based recommendations on the placement of forage crops to strengthen the feed supply of livestock.*

Key words: *livestock, forage crops, yield, productivity, efficiency, placement.*

**ВОПРОСЫ УКРЕПЛЕНИЕ КОРМОВОЙ БАЗЫ В ЖИВОТНОВОДСТВЕ –
ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ПРОДУКТИВНОСТИ**

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируются правовые основы развития животноводческой отрасли Узбекистана, возможности и перспективы Сырдарьинской области в этой сфере. Научно обоснованные рекомендации по размещению кормовых культур для укрепления кормовой базы животноводства.*

Ключвые слова: *животноводства, кормовых культур, урожайность, продуктивность, эффективность, размещения.*

Relevance of the topic. The rapid development of the livestock industry is one of the important conditions for providing our people with cheap and high-quality food products. The “Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030”

identifies increasing the share of fodder crops in the total area of arable land to 12% and increasing livestock productivity as important strategic objectives [1].

Great importance is attached to the further development of this industry in our country. No. PQ-4015 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 13, 2018 “On additional measures for the further development of poultry farming”, March 18, 2019 “Further development and support of the livestock industry” - on support measures” and “Additional measures of state support for the livestock industry” dated 29 January 2020 No. PK-4576. Issues of creating new varieties and hybrids of nutritious and leguminous grain crops, improving their agricultural technologies, conducting primary seed production, selection of super-elite and elite seeds for food supply [2,3].

Also, in order to ensure the implementation of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-5017 dated March 3, 2021 “On additional measures to further support the livestock industry,” it is advisable to organize specialized elite and seed farms, strengthen their material and technical base and locate them in areas with fertile soils [4].

Analysis on the topic. It is known that the country's arable lands are relatively saline, which creates particular difficulties for the development of livestock farming in such conditions. First of all, the yield of nutritious crops is relatively low due to the climatic conditions of saline soil, which, in turn, creates the need to select nutritious crops that are resistant to salinity, improve the technology of their cultivation and improve their nutritional qualities, as well as organize their selection of seeds .

In order to effectively use the area of forage crops, it is necessary first of all to increase their productivity. To this end, it is advisable to start using nutritious crops as main and intermediate crops. In this case, autumn intercropping is important for strengthening the feed supply of livestock. Examples of fall intercrops include triticale, rye, barley, vetch and chickpeas. Since these crops are sown in the fall, their growing season is autumn, winter and spring. With the help of intercropping in early spring (April, May), 250-300 centners of green mass haylage per hectare can be harvested. It is recommended to use catch crops not only as animal feed, but also as green manure (green manure). With the help of this technology, soil fertility is increased. Because the root remains in the soil and turns into humus. This technology increases the productivity of saline soils. Table 1 provides recommendations for the productivity of food crops and the unit of nutrients obtained from them. According to him, it is advisable to place crops wisely depending on soil fertility, type of nutrient crops and their nutrients.

Table 1. Recommendations for the yield (productivity) of food crops and the unit of nutrition obtained from them.

(Using the example of the farm “Avazbek Mamirov” in the Khovos district)

№	Type of food crops	Cultivated area	Productivity c/ha	Total harvested harvest, tons.	Feed units, tons.	In feed units, tons..
1.	Alfalfa	25	120	300	0,45	135
2.	Intermediate crops (wheat, barley, oats)	15	350	525	0,35	184
3.	Corn (for silage)		550	825	0,22	182
4.	Beet	3	500	150	0,1	15
	Total	43	x			515

Author's development based on data from the Avazbek Mamirov farm in the Khavos district.

Harvested cover crop fields can also be replanted with other nutritious crops such as maize, sorghum and African sorghum. In this case, 400-500 c/ha per hectare of sown area. there will be a chance to get green mass. This makes it possible to obtain a double harvest from the cultivated land.

On farms specializing in livestock farming, it is necessary to effectively use every hectare of land allocated for livestock farming, and rational placement of forage crops during harvesting allows livestock to be regularly fed with nutritious feed (Table 2).

Table 2. Scheme for the effective use of land areas allocated for livestock farming and the placement of fodder crops on each farm

№	Types of food crops	Placement of forage crops (on.)	%	Productivity c 1 ha	Gross income, tons.	The resulting harvest Feed unit (tons)
1.	Alfalfa for hay	20	40	120	240	110
2.	Corn for silage			400	1000	200
3.	Intermediate crops for silage	25	50	300	750	262
4.	Beetroot for feed	5	10	800	400	72
	Total	50	100	x	x	644

Author's development.

The crop fields of the Syrdarya region have different levels of salinity. For this reason, the selection, creation and organization of seed production of salt-tolerant plant species and their varieties is a requirement of the time. The primary sowing of intermediate crops in the Syrdarya conditions has not yet been fully established. At the moment, it should be noted that research work is underway to create new varieties of nutritious crops suitable for the natural and climatic conditions of the Syrdarya region. As a result, varieties suitable for the natural climate of our

region have been created, including triticale “Armugon-60”, vetch “Mirzachol-1”, Ara Uzbekistan-30. Thus, promising nutritious crops were selected, including breeding lines L-1 and L-2 of autumn mahsar and vetch, as well as L-1 and L-2 of sorghum. Currently, breeding and breeding work is being carried out with these varieties and lines.

Scientifically based proposals and recommendations using an example in the Syrdarya region. By the end of 2022, the total number of farms and LLCs specializing in livestock breeding in the Syrdarya region will be 706, of which 35,122 are cattle, including 15,686 cows, 41,863 small horned cattle, and 2,964 horses.

According to the supply of barns, there are 26 modern barns, 182 reconstructed and 451 old.

There are 9 special halls equipped with milking equipment, which are found mainly in farms with more than 50 dairy cows. There are 174 portable milking equipment in the region. There are 3 special vehicles for transporting milk.

In the Syrdarya region, the land area allocated to farms specializing in livestock farming amounts to 21,633.9 hectares, including the area of irrigated land - 20,642.5 hectares, which is 95.4% of the total area of allocated land. The remaining 491 hectares are fallow lands and 20.8 hectares are pastures.

There are 843 livestock farms equipped with special equipment, of which 185 are new and 658 are old. In terms of the number of livestock specialists and veterinarians, there are 122 livestock technicians and 62 veterinarians.

However, this situation does not allow the development of livestock farming in the region, or the stable provision of the population with the most necessary food products, such as meat, milk, eggs, as the population grows. The fact that livestock farms are not provided with the necessary basic equipment at the level of demand does not allow increasing the productivity of livestock farming and increasing the efficiency of the financial results of these farms.

Conclusions

We consider it advisable to implement the following measures in order to strengthen the feed base and increase the productivity of livestock farming, effectively meeting the population's demand for meat and dairy products.

1. Under the supervision of the population, more than 90-92 percent of the total number of cattle in the region is raised, and 90-93 percent of livestock products are produced. The supply chain has not been created.

Solutions: Creation in each district of at least 2 farms specializing in growing feed, organizing the sale of feed prepared by them to the population through special stores.

2. The productivity of food crops is low due to the lack of technical means for watering, processing and timely harvesting of feed crops (alfalfa, corn, intermediate crops) grown in medium and small farms.

Solutions: Organize a “Technical Service” consisting of at least two enterprising entrepreneurs in each district and create a system for providing them with start-up capital for carrying out agricultural activities on a contract basis in the fodder fields of livestock farms.

3. Low productivity of areas allocated for fodder crops, efficient use of available fodder areas.

Solutions: Increase productivity through efficient use of allocated feeding areas and obtaining 10-12 tons of feed units per hectare of feeding area.

4. High-yielding seeds of forage crops grown by livestock farms are not enough and do not cover the current need.

Solutions: Further development of the activities of farms specializing in growing seeds of nutritious crops in the region, establish cooperation with scientific institutions for growing seeds of nutritious crops, install equipment for cleaning alfalfa seeds in seed farms.

5. Lack of equipment for harvesting and harvesting food crops and making arrangements for their procurement abroad.

Solutions: Exemption from state duty on harvesting equipment purchased abroad for timely and high-quality harvesting of food crops grown on livestock farms in the region.

6. There is no need to bring into the country varieties of crops (for silage and haylage) rich in succulent feed, grown in countries with a developed livestock industry, and conduct experiments on a large scale on a scientific basis.

Solutions: It will be possible to provide cheap, high-quality and low-cost roughage and succulent feed for livestock to households.

7. Effective use and implementation of scientific achievements and the scientific approach in strengthening the livestock and feed base.

Solutions: To develop livestock farming and create a strong feed base, it is necessary to introduce scientific achievements and innovative technologies into every farming and manufacturing enterprise.

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